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A comprehensive description of the circulating tumor cell: GIMAP4.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

The circulating tumor cell (CTC) is most likely responsible for effective metastasis (1-3). We measured total transcription in circulating tumor cells isolated from the blood of women with stage IV breast cancer to define at the molecular level the most significant changes that accompany dissemination in a migrating tumor cell population (4) and integrated these with transcriptomic study of the circulating tumor cell in humans with metastatic prostate cancer (5). We identify here GIMAP4 as a differentially expressed target in the circulating tumor cell in humans with cancer.

1 Circulating tumor cells are likely the tumor cell population that function in dissemination and do so by
2 seeding distant organ sites. We defined the CTC transcriptome, describing the most significant changes
3 by target and using normal blood cells from the peripheral blood as a control reference transcriptome.

4 Results

5 **Figure 1:** GIMAP4 is differentially expressed and silenced in the circulating tumor cell.

6 I. CTC from humans with stage IV breast cancer (peripheral blood).

7 $n=18$ normal cells from the peripheral blood (human)

8 $n=14$ circulating tumor cells; humans with stage IV breast cancer; peripheral blood

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
55303	1.66E-13	0.715	7.3736365	5.2748429	280.55	GIMAP4	59/21908	99.7

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10 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in circulating tumor cells isolated from the
11 peripheral blood of women with stage IV breast cancer and transcription in normal cells of the blood (5),
12 we discovered differential expression of GTPase, IMAP family member 4, encoded by *GIMAP4* in the CTC
13 humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of GIMAP4 changed more than 99% of the human transcriptome
14 when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 21,908 transcripts
15 ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating decreased quantity of GIMAP4 messenger RNA in the
16 CTC, indicating down-regulation of GIMAP4 disease progression and metastasis from primary tumor to
17 CTC during the tumor life cycle.

18 II. CTC from humans with stage IV breast cancer (peripheral blood).

19 $n=1$ normal white blood cells from the peripheral blood (human)

20 $n=5$ circulating tumor cells; humans with metastatic prostate cancer ; peripheral blood

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
25793	6.34E-11	0.781	6.535556	5.10274	2.83E+04	FBXO7	63/26194	99.8

21 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the CTC of humans with prostate cancer
22 relative to normal white blood cells using a second microarray dataset (6) from independent
23 investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of GIMAP4 in humans
24 with metastatic solid tumor type. (**Chart 2**). The expression of GIMAP4 here changed more than 99% of
25 the human transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case,
26 26,194 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating decreased quantity of GIMAP4
27 messenger RNA in the CTC indicating down-regulation of GIMAP4 disease progression and metastasis
28 from primary tumor to CTC during the tumor life cycle.

Thus, differential and decreased expression of GIMAP4 is a defining change of the circulating tumor
cell gene expression signature in humans with metastatic breast cancer.

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Discussion

We provided evidence here that GIMAP4 is a molecular target of modulation in the CTC. This included a panel of cell surface markers, some of whose expression was conserved as marking the CTC in prostate cancer but of some of whose expression was specific to the circulating tumor cell in humans with metastatic breast cancer.

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Methods

We utilized GSE113890 (4) for this transcriptome study of the circulating tumor cell in humans with cancer, measuring whole transcription in CTC isolated from peripheral blood from humans with stage IV breast cancer, as compared to normal cells from the peripheral blood (along with a second dataset GSE202650 (5) studying the CTC in humans with prostate cancer for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).